

Study on the Mechanism and Pattern of Synergistic Removal of Phosphorus in Wastewater by Steel Slag

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, phosphorus has become a major pollutant in rivers and lakes, causing eutrophication of water bodies. When the phosphorus concentration in water exceeds a certain limit, it triggers massive algal proliferation, forming algal blooms, which seriously affects the balance of the aquatic ecosystem. Currently, China has accumulated over 1 billion tons of waste steel slag, and the crushed steel slag has characteristics such as high specific surface area and high porosity, which are favorable for phosphorus removal. This project explores and verifies the synergistic phosphorus removal mechanism of physical adsorption and chemical adsorption (forming HAP precipitate) of steel slag for phosphorus in sewage through experiments and tests such as SEM and XRD. The research was carried out in terms of adsorption time, initial phosphorus concentration of the effluent and safety of phosphorus removal from steel slag. And it is concluded that the optimal adsorption time for steel slag phosphorus removal is 20 minutes, the initial phosphorus concentration has a small impact on the phosphorus removal rate of steel slag, and steel slag can effectively treat high-concentration phosphorus-containing sewage; the heavy metal content in the leaching solution of steel slag is lower than the first-level emission concentration limit in the comprehensive sewage discharge standard, and steel slag can achieve reliable and safe phosphorus removal. This study provides new ideas for combining the utilization of solid waste steel slag with water pollution control.

Keywords: steel slag, phosphorus-containing wastewater, safety, chemical adsorption, physical adsorption

1 Research Background

I live in a residential area in Beijing, China. On the north side of the residential area, there is a small river named Beixiaohe. A few years ago, the water in this river was heavily polluted and smelled terrible, so much so that some property owners even called it the "Little Stinking River". Every time I passed by this river, I had to take a detour and thought: When will Beixiaohe become clear? With Beijing's emphasis on sewage treatment, Beixiaohe has gradually become clearer and the smell has disappeared. This made me realize the importance of sewage treatment. By consulting relevant information, I learned that in recent years, phosphorus has become the primary pollutant in rivers and lakes. Excessive phosphorus concentration in water bodies can lead to eutrophication, causing excessive reproduction of algae and other organisms, forming the "water bloom" phenomenon. After the death of algae, a large number of microorganisms decompose the corpses, reducing dissolved oxygen in the water and leading to the death of aquatic organisms, ultimately accelerating the deterioration of water quality. Therefore, phosphorus content is an important indicator for sewage monitoring. Currently, although various regions in China have carried out a series of total phosphorus pollution control efforts, the pollution problems of "three phosphors" (phosphate mines, phosphorus chemical enterprises, and phosphogypsum ponds) have not been fundamentally resolved. Many parts of China's rivers have shown locally high total phosphorus values, and many sections have high pollution intensity during the flood season. Phosphorus pollution control still has a long way to go (Qin et al., 2018).

Phosphorus primarily exists in three forms: inorganic phosphorus compounds, phosphorus-containing organics, and PH_3 (phosphine). Inorganic phosphorus primarily includes orthophosphates and metaphosphates. Metaphosphates are highly unstable and tend to convert into orthophosphates in aerobic environments (Zhong, 2018). They are commonly found in fertilizers, electroplating, and wastewater from phosphorus chemical plants. Organic phosphorus primarily refers to organic phosphorus pesticides, which are insoluble in water. They typically enter water bodies through agricultural fertilization, pesticide use, food residues, industrial wastewater, and sediment release. PH_3 is also a form of phosphorus, possessing strong reducing properties. It can easily convert into dissolved phosphates under conditions of light and oxygen (Chang et al., 2005; Chen, 2003). According to the Class A emission requirements of the "Emission Standards for Pollutants from Municipal Wastewater Treatment Plants" (GB18918-2002), the total phosphorus content in water bodies must be less than 0.5 mg/L.

Currently, there are three commonly used methods for phosphorus removal: physical phosphorus removal, chemical phosphorus removal, and biological phosphorus removal (see Table 1).

Table 1 Phosphorus removal methods

Methods	Advantages	Disadvantages
Physical phosphorus removal method	Low energy consumption, minimal pollution, fast removal, and recyclability	The adsorption capacity of biomass is relatively small, and it is greatly influenced by pH value and several specific anions. Moreover, physical phosphorus removal methods are costly and technically complex
Chemical phosphorus removal method	The treatment effect is relatively stable, with a wide range of applications and simple operation	It will generate a large amount of sludge, which is difficult to handle. And more chemical reagents will be used, causing secondary pollution of the environment and increasing the treatment cost
Biological phosphorus removal method	Simple process, low processing cost, minimal pollution, energy conservation, and wide range of applicability	The stability and flexibility are relatively poor, and it is easily affected by the temperature and pH of the wastewater

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of artificial wetland for wastewater treatment

In recent years, the use of artificial wetlands for wastewater treatment has been widely applied. Artificial wetland wastewater treatment technology is a technology that uses the physical, chemical, and biological triple synergies of soil, artificial media, plants, and microorganisms to treat wastewater by artificially constructing and controlling to run the ground similar to swamps, and by controlling the sewage to be dispensed onto the wetland, so that the sewage will flow in a certain direction in the wetland soil crevices and surfaces, as shown in Figure 1. On the one hand, artificial wetlands can serve as landscapes for people to enjoy. On the other hand, compared to conventional wastewater treatment plants, the construction cost of artificial wetlands is a fraction of the latter, and the cost per cubic meter of wastewater treatment is one-tenth of the latter(Wang & Cao, 2008), showing a very obvious cost advantage.

China is a major steel producer, with annual crude steel output exceeding half of the world's total. Steel slag, a by-product generated during the steelmaking process, primarily consists of oxides of calcium, iron, silicon, magnesium, and minor amounts of aluminum, manganese, phosphorus, etc. Its production accounts for approximately 15% to 20% of crude steel output. Currently, the accumulation of steel slag in China exceeds 1 billion tons. The elements contained in steel slag, such as calcium (Ca), iron (Fe), aluminum (Al), magnesium (Mg), and silicon (Si), can react with phosphate radicals to form phosphate precipitates through chemical adsorption(Wang et al., 2009). Additionally, steel slag's high specific surface area and porosity endow it with strong adsorption capabilities through physical adsorption(Shi, 2011; Yang et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2018). As a phosphate adsorption material, steel slag holds significant development potential. This study proposes utilizing steel slag as an adsorption medium in artificial wetlands for wastewater phosphorus removal, aiming to achieve the objective of treating waste with waste.

2 Research Purpose

- (1) Explore and verify the removal mechanism of phosphorus in wastewater by steel slag;
- (2) Investigate the influence of different treatment durations and initial phosphorus concentration in wastewater on the phosphorus removal efficiency from wastewater;
- (3) Evaluate the leaching of heavy metal ions in steel slag during the dephosphorization process, and assess the safety of dephosphorization using steel slag;

(4) Provide new insights for integrating the resource utilization of solid waste steel slag with water pollution control.

3 Research Methods

3.1 Experimental Equipment

0.45 μ m microporous membrane, three-neck flask, filtration device, graduated cylinder, electronic balance, filter screen, grinder, beaker, magnetic stirring water bath, scanning electron microscope (SEM), X-ray diffractometer (XRD), inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) (see Attachment 1).

3.2 Experimental Materials

Deionized water, potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4), and steel slag (see Figures 2 and 3).

Fig. 2 Potassium dihydrogen phosphate

Fig. 3 Steel slag

3.3 Simulated Wastewater

Prepare potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4) solutions of different concentrations using deionized water to simulate wastewater.

3.4 Selection of Steel Slag

The steel slag used is a solid waste generated during the steel-making process, and its main components are shown in Table 2. Based on the adsorption principle, the smaller the particle

size of steel slag, the larger its specific surface area, which is more conducive to the removal of phosphorus. However, the smaller the particle size of steel slag, the more energy is consumed for crushing and grinding steel slag in practical applications. Considering both the phosphorus removal effect and cost, steel slag with a particle size of 270-1700 μm is selected as the adsorption substrate.

Table 2 Main Components of Steel Slag

Contents	CaO	SiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	FeO	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	P ₂ O ₅	MnO	TiO ₂	V ₂ O ₅	Cr ₂ O ₃	f-CaO	Others
wt/%	45.34	11.41	14.51	15.80	4.35	1.31	2.42	2.19	1.27	0.85	0.25	2.75	0.30

3.5 Characterization Methods

(1) X-ray Diffraction Analysis (XRD)

The original steel slag and the residual steel slag filtered by vacuum after the removal of phosphorus from the wastewater were put into a vacuum drying oven at a drying temperature of 80 °C. After drying for 24 hours, grind it and sieve it through a 75 μm (200 mesh) sieve. Then, use a Japanese Marcop MXP21VAHF X-ray diffractometer to measure the original steel slag and the residual slag after the phosphorus removal adsorption reaction, with a scanning range of 5°~80°, a working voltage of 40 kV, and a working current of 40 mA.

(2) Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)

The raw steel slag as well as the filtered steel slag from the removal of phosphorus from the wastewater were dried in a desiccator for 24 h, and then the slag powder was glued to the sample stage with conductive adhesive. Observe the micro-morphology of the steel slag before and after adsorption using a ZEISS EVO18 scanning electron microscope, and observe the micro-morphology of the sample using secondary electron mode. It is necessary to spray gold on the sample surface. The working voltage of the scanning electron microscope is 20 kV, and the vacuum degree is 2.0×10^{-5} Torr.

(3) Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (ICP-MS)

Pour the mixture of steel slag, which has undergone adsorption reaction for phosphorus removal from wastewater, and KH_2PO_4 aqueous solution into a vacuum filtration device. Test the P content of the filtrate that enters the conical flask. Dry the residual slag left on the filter paper and wait for further testing and observation. Since the detection limit of ICP-MS is mostly at the ppt (ng/L) level, and the highest concentration of KH_2PO_4 in this experiment can reach 100 ppm (mg/L), all liquids in this experiment were diluted. This experiment utilizes the ICAPRQ model inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer from Thermo Fisher Scientific for detection.

3.6 Experimental Steps

This study is based on the application of steel slag in artificial wetlands for wastewater treatment, and investigates the removal pattern of phosphorus in wastewater by steel slag. The specific steps are as follows:

(1) Study the removal rate of phosphorus in wastewater by steel slag under different treatment times, and determine the optimal treatment time.

Using the chemical potassium dihydrogen phosphate to prepare water samples with varying phosphorus content to simulate wastewater. Treating wastewater with steel slag, and referencing the phosphorus content in the treated water samples, studying the impact of adsorption time on the phosphorus removal efficiency of steel slag, and determining the optimal adsorption time.

Prepare 200 mL of phosphate solution with an initial concentration of 50 mg/L using KH_2PO_4 and deionized water, and place it in a 500 mL three-neck flask. Weigh (3.0 ± 0.02) g of steel slag with a particle size ranging from 270 μm to 1700 μm and place it into the three-neck flask. Seal the flask with a rubber stopper and place it in a constant temperature magnetic stirring water bath at 25 °C and 300 r/min for stirring. Set the treatment times to 1, 2, 3, 5, 10, 20, and 30 minutes, respectively. After the adsorption process is complete, allow it to stand for 15 minutes. Filter the phosphate solution using a 0.45 μm microporous membrane and filtration device, and measure its phosphorus (P) mass concentration. Draw an adsorption time-phosphorus removal rate curve to determine the optimal adsorption time for the initial concentration of 50 mg/L phosphate solution.

(2) Determine the optimal treatment time, study the treatment effect of steel slag on wastewater with different initial phosphorus concentrations, and verify whether steel slag can treat wastewater with high phosphorus content.

Prepare wastewater with four different phosphate concentrations (25, 50, 75, and 100 mg/L), using the optimal treatment time obtained from the previous experiment. Follow the same procedure as in the previous experiment to perform phosphorus removal. Plot the removal rate curves for different initial phosphorus concentrations, and determine the applicable phosphorus concentration range for steel slag phosphorus removal and the phosphorus removal capacity of steel slag.

(3) Study the safety of treating wastewater with steel slag, specifically verifying whether heavy metals are leaching from steel slag into the wastewater during the treatment process, resulting in excessive levels of heavy metals in the wastewater.

Detecting whether the treated water sample contains heavy metals from steel slag and verifying the safety of using steel slag to treat wastewater are important indicators for determining whether steel slag can be utilized for wastewater treatment. Weigh 50 g of steel slag and place it into a three-necked flask with a capacity of 1 L. Add 0.5 L of deionized water according to the liquid-solid ratio of 10:1 (L:kg), tightly close the flask, and secure it in a magnetic stirring thermostatic water bath. Set the stirring frequency to 300 r/min and stir at room temperature for 8 hours. Then, remove the three-necked flask. Allow the solution to stand for 16 hours, filter it using a 0.45 μm microporous membrane and filtration device, and collect the leachate. Send it to the testing center and use an ICP spectrometer to detect the content of copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), selenium (Se), arsenic (As), lead (Pb), and cadmium (Cd) in the leachate.

(4) Utilize XRD and SEM to examine the mineral phases and microstructure of both the original steel slag and the steel slag after phosphorus removal from wastewater. Compare the differences between the steel slag before and after phosphorus removal, and explore and verify the mechanism by which steel slag removes phosphorus from wastewater.

4 Research Results and Analysis

The removal of phosphates from wastewater by steel slag primarily involves two mechanisms: physical adsorption and chemical adsorption. Physical adsorption is caused by

intermolecular forces (Van der Waals forces), which refers to the physical adsorption of phosphates by metal oxides in steel slag. The main mechanism of chemisorption is that the dissociated Ca^{2+} in the steel slag and PO_4^{3-} in the wastewater generate supersaturated phosphate precipitation onto the surface of the steel slag, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4 Reaction mechanism of phosphorus removal from wastewater by steel slag

The combined mechanisms of physical adsorption and chemical adsorption facilitate the effective removal of phosphates from wastewater by steel slag. Among them, chemical adsorption is considered to be the main approach for removing phosphorus from ordinary steel slag (Zhao & Zhou, 2009; Li et al., 2011). Various metal oxides contained in sewage react with phosphate through a series of chemical reactions to form precipitates, achieving the purpose of removing phosphorus. The calcium dissolved from steel slag combines with phosphate in wastewater to form calcium phosphates, which are not a single type but may include amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP), dicalcium phosphate (DCP), dicalcium phosphate dehydrate (DCPD), octacalcium phosphate (OCP), tricalcium phosphate (TCP), hydroxyapatite (HAP), and fluorapatite (FAP). The formation of calcium phosphate precipitates usually follows Ostwald's "stage rule", which means that less stable compounds are precipitated first, and then recrystallized to form the most thermodynamically stable hydroxyapatite. During the treatment of wastewater with steel slag, various calcium

phosphate phases are formed, depending on the pH value and composition of the solution. The type of final precipitate depends on whether it is supersaturated.

Generally, the chemical process of calcium oxide in steel slag in water follows equation (1). When the pH value is approximately 11.4, dissolved calcium ions react with phosphates to form $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{OH})$ (HAP) precipitate, as shown in equation (2).

4.1 Impact of Adsorption Time on Phosphorus Removal from Wastewater Using Steel Slag

Figure 5 shows the adsorption time-phosphorus concentration and phosphorus removal curves. As shown in the figure, adsorption time significantly influences the phosphorus removal efficiency from steel slag. The phosphorus removal rate for a phosphate solution with an initial mass concentration of 50 mg/L rapidly increases in the early stages and then tends to level off over time. It can be observed from the graph that the removal rate reaches 98.82% at 20 minutes, while at 30 minutes, it increases slightly to 99.01%, representing only a 0.19 percentage point increase. Considering both time and removal efficiency comprehensively, the optimal adsorption time is determined to be 20 minutes.

As can be inferred from the above, as the adsorption time increases, the adsorption rate of phosphorus solution by steel slag decreases. This is because, as the adsorption reaction proceeds, the mass concentration of phosphate ions in the phosphate solution decreases, thereby reducing the driving force for adsorption. The pattern of change in the adsorption rate conforms to the three-stage theory of phosphorus removal adsorption process proposed by Han Yun et al. (Hu et al., 2019): the first stage is the rapid adsorption phase, the second stage is the slow adsorption phase, and the third stage is the final adsorption equilibrium phase.

Fig. 5 Plot of adsorption time versus phosphorus concentration and phosphorus removal rate

4.2 Impact of Initial Phosphorus Concentration on the Phosphorus Removal Rate from Wastewater

Under different concentrations of potassium dihydrogen phosphate, the phosphorus concentration in water samples after 20 minutes of adsorption by steel slag and its removal rate were calculated based on experimental results. A relationship curve between the initial phosphate concentration of wastewater and the phosphorus concentration and removal rate after treatment was plotted (see Figure 6). When the concentration of potassium dihydrogen phosphate was increased from 25 mg/L to 100 mg/L, the phosphorus removal rate of steel slag to phosphate solution showed a decreasing trend as a whole, but the phosphorus removal rate of all groups could reach about 90%. This indicates that the initial concentration has a small impact on the phosphorus removal efficiency of steel slag, which can effectively treat wastewater with high phosphorus content.

Fig. 6 Relationship between initial phosphate concentration in wastewater and the concentration of phosphorus after treatment, as well as the phosphorus removal rate

4.3 Analysis of Phase Composition and Microstructure of Steel Slag before and after Sewage Treatment

(1) Phase Composition

The XRD pattern of the original steel slag is shown in Figure 7(a), where the main mineral phases are $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$, $\alpha\text{-Ca}_2\text{SiO}_4$, $\beta\text{-Ca}_2\text{SiO}_4$, and RO phase. The XRD pattern of the steel slag after sewage treatment is shown in Figure 8(b), where the main mineral phase is $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{OH})$ (HAP). Based on the comparison of the two patterns and previous studies, during the removal of phosphorus from sewage, CaO and Ca_2SiO_4 undergo hydrolysis first, releasing Ca^{2+} . Subsequently, Ca^{2+} reacts chemically with PO_4^{3-} in the sewage to form hydroxyapatite precipitate (HAP). Due to the porous surface of the steel slag, which is prone to serving as a nucleation site for crystallization, HAP aggregates on the surface of the steel slag under the action of Van der Waals forces.

Fig. 7 XRD patterns of raw steel slag and steel slag after sewage treatment (a) XRD of raw steel slag (b) XRD of steel slag after sewage treatment

(2) Microstructure

Based on the analysis in Sections 4.1 and 4.2, I conducted an analysis on the mineral phase composition and microstructure of steel slag before and after sewage treatment. The changes in microstructural morphology of steel slag before and after adsorption of P for sewage treatment, observed using SEM, are shown in Figure 8, and the corresponding energy spectrum data are presented in Table 3. Comparing the results, it is evident that there is a significant difference in the microstructure of steel slag particles before and after sewage treatment. As can be seen from the figure, before adsorption of P for sewage treatment, the steel slag surface is relatively smooth, and the steel slag appears as irregular granules. After sewage treatment, many columnar or flaky grayish-white crystalline phases appear on the steel slag surface. According to the energy spectrum data, the phosphorus content in the original steel slag is very low. After adsorption and phosphorus removal, the phosphorus content on the steel slag surface increases significantly. Therefore, these columnar objects are mainly phosphorus-containing phases. These observations indicate that the adsorption of P by steel slag is achieved through the formation of Ca-P precipitates.

Fig. 8 (a) and (b) show the SEM images of the original steel slag surface, while (c) and (d) depict the SEM images of the steel slag surface after the adsorption reaction

Table 3 Energy spectrum data of original steel slag and steel slag after adsorption

Number	O/ %	Mg/ %	Al/ %	Si/ %	P/ %	Ca/ %	Ti/ %	V/ %	Cr/ %	Mn/ %	Fe/ %
1	33.58	4.61	0.86	1.41	—	15.15	—	—	0.44	2.28	41.67
2	50.06	1.55	19.96	4.7	0.81	14.33	—	0.29	—	0.39	7.9
3	74.07	0.82	0.35	1.38	7.57	—	11.95	—	0.22	0.31	3.33
4	69.18	—	—	0.94	11.69	16.74	—	—	—	—	1.46

Based on previous research and the results of this experiment, it is concluded that the primary mechanism for phosphorus removal from steel slag under the conditions of this experiment is as follows: phosphorus-containing substances adhere to the surface of steel slag through physical adsorption. Simultaneously, and more importantly, a chemical adsorption process occurs, where calcium oxides and hydroxides dissolved from steel slag react chemically with phosphate radicals, subsequently forming phosphate compounds that precipitate on the surface of steel slag. The resulting off-white precipitate is primarily composed of Ca-P precipitates, with the main component being $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{OH})$ (HAP).

4.4 Safety Assessment of Phosphorus Removal from Steel Slag

The utilization of adsorbent materials is predicated on the premise of not generating secondary pollution, as the introduction of secondary pollutants would escalate subsequent water treatment costs. Given the complex composition of steel slag, which contains various heavy metal elements, the safety of steel slag application in wastewater treatment must be taken into account. Table 4 presents the concentrations of Cu, Zn, Cd, As, Pb, and Hg in steel slag leachate. Evidently, the concentrations of these elements in the steel slag leachate are below the Class I emission concentration limits stipulated in the Integrated Wastewater Discharge Standard, indicating that the application of steel slag in wastewater treatment is safe.

Table 4 Content of toxic heavy metals in steel slag leachate

Element	Cu	Zn	Cd	As	Pb	Hg
Concentration (mg/L)	0.151	0.048	0.083	0.052	0.212	0.046
Limit value of hazardous component concentration in leachate, mg/L(Standardization Administration of China, 1998)	0.5	2.0	0.1	0.5	1.0	0.05

5 Preliminary Design and Calculation for Engineering Applications

Steel slag is applied in artificial wetlands for sewage phosphorus removal. After a certain service life, the steel slag needs to be replaced. However, the replaced steel slag can still be used for the improvement of acidic soil, achieving the ultimate utilization of steel slag. Referring to the Technical Code for Constructed Wetland Wastewater Treatment Engineering (HJ 2005-2010), a subsurface flow constructed wetland is selected. Drawing on the above experimental results, steel slag is used as the filler material in the constructed wetland for sewage phosphorus removal. The application design and calculation are as follows:

The proposed artificial wetland covers a total area of 2.0 hectares. The main body of the wetland is filled with steel slag to a depth of 1.2 meters, and the surface layer is paved with 200 mm-thick pebbles as a planting layer for emergent plants with strong purification capabilities. The effective water depth is 1.2 meters, and the hydraulic retention time is set to 24 hours. The wetland has a daily water treatment capacity of 24,000 cubic meters, reducing the total phosphorus concentration from 0.35 mg/L to below 0.20 mg/L. Assuming a maximum adsorption capacity of steel slag of 2.5 mg/g, the fill material needs to be replaced once every 10 years, with a minimum requirement of approximately 5,256 tons of steel slag per replacement. Based on the empirical value of bulk density of 2.5 t/m³(Zheng et al., 2022), the steel slag fill material for the wetland is 60,000 tons, which is more than 10 times the minimum requirement and fully meets the phosphorus removal demand. According to the fact that 1.5-5 tons of steel slag can treat 1 hectare of acidic soil(Wei, 2015), a 2.0-hectare artificial wetland can treat approximately 12,000-40,000 hectares of acidic soil after one replacement of fill material. It is reported that there are 204 million hectares of acidic soil in China. After large-scale improvement, these lands will greatly benefit agricultural development and income increase for farmers in China.

6 Research Conclusions

Given the significant advantages of steel slag in the phosphorus removal process, this paper takes steel slag as the research object. Through comparative experiments, it explores the impact of adsorption time and initial phosphorus concentration in wastewater on the phosphorus removal efficiency of steel slag. Additionally, it examines the content of heavy metals in the treated wastewater to verify its safety. The experimental results indicate that:

(1) Adsorption time significantly affects the phosphorus removal efficiency of steel slag. Considering both the phosphorus removal efficiency and economic cost, this study suggests that the optimal adsorption time is 20 minutes.

(2) The phosphorus removal rate of steel slag for phosphate solutions with initial mass concentrations of 25, 50, 75, and 100 mg/L generally showed a decreasing trend. However, the phosphorus removal rate in each group could reach around 90%, indicating that the initial concentration of phosphate has little effect on the phosphorus removal rate. Steel slag can effectively treat wastewater with high phosphorus content.

(3) Steel slag removes phosphate from wastewater through physical and chemical adsorption mechanisms. Before and after adsorption, the main phase on the surface of steel slag transforms from irregular granular CaO and Ca_2SiO_4 phases to needle-like $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{OH})$ phase. During the wastewater treatment process, the main method is to generate $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{OH})$ (HAP) precipitate to remove PO_4^{3-} in the wastewater, ultimately achieving effective removal of P from the wastewater.

(4) This study confirms that the contents of heavy metals such as Fe, Zn, As, Cd, Cu, and Pb in the leaching solution of steel slag meet the first-level emission concentration limits specified in the Integrated Wastewater Discharge Standard, indicating that the application of steel slag in wastewater phosphorus removal is safe.

(6) A 2.0-hectare artificial wetland can treat 24,000 cubic meters of water per day. After 10 years of use, the replaced steel slag filler can treat approximately 12,000-40,000 hectares of acidic soil.

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